

The multiple cropping experiment from 1985-86 to 1986-87 consisted of seven cropping patterns (see table). Two-year rotations were maintained so that a rice - sugarcane sequence could be completed for comparison. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Soil of the experimental area was silty-clay with pH 8.2, 0.6% organic C, and 272.0, 32.4, and 131.5 kg/ha available N, P₂O₅, and K₂O, respectively. Maximum water depth was 67 cm in 1985-86, 81 cm in 1986-87.

Varieties used were deepwater rice (DWR) variety Janki, sweet potato RS5 and Cross-4, jute JRC321, black gram T9, and green gram G65.

Depending upon the land situation, DWR may be sown from Feb to Jun. In all the intercropping sequences, the rice crop was sown in the last week of Feb and fertilized after harvest of the intercrops with 20 kg N/ha applied as

topdressing. In rotational treatments, such as rice - sweet potato and rice - sugarcane - green gram, rice was sown in mid-Jun. Sweet potato and sugarcane were planted after the harvest of rice in Feb.

Among the crop sequences, rice -

sesame and rice - sweet potato cross-4 produced significantly more equivalent rice yield per year (see table). In terms of cost:benefit ratio, rice - green gram was statistically superior to rice - sweet potato cross-4. □

Production potential, production efficiency, cost: return ratio of cropping sequences in North Bihar, India.

Cropping sequence		Crop yield (t/ha)				Equivalent rice grain yield (t/ha per yr)	Cost: return ratio
		1985-86		1986-87			
1985-86	1986-87	Main crop	Subsequent crop	Main crop	Subsequent crop		
Rice + sesame	Rice + sesame	2.1	0.4	1.9	0.5	4.2	1.37
Rice - sweet potato	Rice - sweet potato	1.9	15.2	1.9	14.3	3.7	0.54
Rice - sweet potato	Rice - sweet potato	2.1	16.6	2.0	17.1	4.2	0.73
Rice + jute for fiber	Rice + jute for fiber	1.8	0.6	1.9	0.5	3.0	0.49
Rice - sugarcane - green gram		2.2	-	33.5	-	0.5	3.3
Rice + black gram	Rice + black gram	2.1	0.3	2.2	0.3	2.3	0.68
Rice + black gram	Rice + black gram	2.2	0.5	2.1	0.5	3.4	0.92
LSD (0.05)		-	-	-	-	0.3	0.18

Farming systems—irrigated rice

Transplanted rice-based cropping sequences in an irrigation canal command area of Rajasthan

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The canal command area of Rajasthan has assured irrigation. Rice is a major wet season (Jun-Oct) crop. We evaluated some rice-based cropping sequences involving improved cultivars of wheat *Triticum aestivum*, barley *Hordium vulgare*, berseem *Trifolium alexan-*

drinum, and chickpea *Cicer arietinum* to follow rice in the dry season (DS) 1981-85.

Experimental soil was Vertisol with pH 7.6 and 0.61% organic C. Medium-duration (130-135 d) Jaya rice variety was transplanted the first week of Jul. DS crops were sown in Nov. Recommended fertilizer rates

were 120-60-30 kg NPK/ha for rice, 100-60-30 for wheat, 60-30-0 for barley, 25-30-0 for berseem, and 25-40-0 for chickpea.

Rice - berseem gave the highest production and benefit:cost ratio (see table). Its net return (\$1,812.5/ha) was 42% higher than that of the dominant rice - wheat cropping sequence. □

Grain yields and returns from rice-based cropping sequences in irrigation canal command area of Rajasthan, Kota, India, 1981-85.

Crop sequence	Mean grain yield (t/ha)		Gross return (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio
	Wet season	Dry season			
Rice - berseem	7.0	20 ^a + 0.4	2437.5	1812.5	2.90
Rice - chickpea	7.1	1.4	1762.5	1237.5	2.36
Rice - wheat	6.8	3.2	1837.5	1275.0	2.26
Rice - barley	6.7	3.8	1725.0	1187.5	2.21

^aBerseem as green fodder.

Rice-based cropping systems for Andhra Pradesh

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Wet season rice followed by alternate dry season crops occupies most of the area under irrigation in AP. We evaluated rice - sunflower, rice - safflower, rice - groundnut, and rice - maize cropping sequences in 1988-89 and 1989-90. Rice variety WGL22245 was transplanted at 20- × 10-cm spacing for the

wet season crop; sunflower cultivar Mordan, safflower Manjira, groundnut ICGS-11, and maize EH4012 were the dry season crops.

Soil was sandy clay loam, pH 8.1 (clay 20-27%, silt 8-10%, sand 65-70%), low to medium in available N (250-300 kg/ha), high in available P (30 kg/ha) and